

Enhancing Concrete Properties through Fly Ash Utilization: An Experimental Approach

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ABSTRACT–Fly Ash is becoming increasingly used as a partly alternative for cement in concrete. This technique's growing popularity stems from its potential benefits for sustainability and resource conservation. Many studies have been conducted to understand more about the application of Fly Ash in concrete. These tests employ the partial substitution method, in which a portion of the cement component in concrete mixtures is replaced with Fly Ash. This study intends to evaluate the impact of partially replacing cement in concrete with Fly Ash (0%, 10%, 25%, 35%, 40%, and 50%) on the compressive strength of M20 grade concrete. Test results show that adding Fly Ash to concrete improves its workability. The testing results showed that adding Fly Ash to the concrete boosted its compressive strength up to a 25% replacement level in cement. Through this long experimental project, the researchers hoped to gain a thorough understanding of how Fly Ash incorporation impacts the workability and compressive strength of concrete.

KEYWORDS: Fly Ash, Concrete, Workability, Strength, Curing.

I. NOMENCLATURE SECTION:

In this section the entire abbreviations and notation used throughout the article is tabulated in the following Table I. The variables used in the equations are not included in this table.

TABLE I.
ABBREVIATION OF THE USED NOTATION IN THIS ARTICLE.

<i>Notation</i>	Meaning
FA	Fly Ash
CS	Compressive Strength
ACS	Average Compressive Strength
FIA	Fine Aggregates
CA	Coarse Aggregates

II. INTRODUCTION

Pozzolans are substances with minimal or negligible inherent cementing attributes. However, in the presence of lime and water, they can create cement. These minerals are normally supplied from natural sources, however a significant fraction of modern pozzolans are created from the combustion of powdered coal during the creation of electricity. Concrete's components typically include fine aggregate, coarse aggregate, cement, and water. However, the manufacture of cement presents serious environmental problems, particularly because it emits carbon dioxide (CO₂), a major greenhouse gas that contributes to global warming. Recognizing the negative impacts of cement manufacture, many alternatives have been investigated, including the use of FA, pulverized granulated blast furnace slag, rice husk and silica fume. FA, in particular, stands out as a more cost-effective option than Portland cement, making it economically viable for significant replacement ratios. The use of considerable volumes of FA is believed to have resulted in a 25% decrease in material costs during the construction of the Upper Stillwater Dam, demonstrating the potential for major economic benefits. By adding these alternative elements into concrete manufacturing, it is possible to alleviate the environmental issues connected with cement while also providing economic benefits. The rising use of FA and other pozzolanic materials demonstrates the possibility for a more sustainable approach to building, which aligns with the goal of lowering carbon footprints and promoting environmentally friendly practices in the sector. Using FA in concrete provides substantial environmental benefits, such as boosting durability and extending the life of structures. When FA is utilized

to replace or supplant made cement, there is a net reduction in energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, and other harmful air pollutants. It decreases the quantity of coal combustion products that need to be disposed of in landfills while also conserving other natural resources and commodities.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW:

The current investigation seeks to explore the impact of FA on concrete through the partial substitution of cement with FA ranging from 0% to 50%. Numerous prior studies have delved into examining how FA affects different aspects of concrete quality across various ages and grades. This publication incorporates a review of selected research endeavors pertaining to the influence of FA on concrete properties. The influence of FA additive on concrete qualities was investigated [1], and it was discovered that normal consistency improves as cement grade and FA content increase. It was also determined that using FA increases the workability of concrete. Furthermore, it was discovered that the CS of concrete increases with the grade of cement. With an increase in FA content across all grades of Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC), there is a corresponding decrease in concrete strength. This reduction is more pronounced during the initial stages compared to later stages of concrete curing. Additionally, it was observed that FA concrete exhibits superior durability in comparison to standard OPC concrete. The impact of partially substituting cement with FA on CS [2]. The study revealed that the incorporation of FA tends to delay the setting time of concrete. Moreover, it was found that the rate of strength development at various ages correlates with both the water-to-cement (w/c) ratio and the proportion of FA in the concrete mixture. Additionally, as the percentage of FA in the concrete mix increased, there was a corresponding decrease in the modulus of elasticity for a constant w/c ratio. The study [3] examined how partial substitution of FA affects CS. Results revealed that substituting 10% and 25% of cement with FA led to increased CS at 3, 7, and 28 days, respectively. The study [4] explored how FA impacts concrete properties, revealing that as the water-to-cement (w/c) ratio and FA content increased, slump loss also escalated. Additionally, it was found that concrete with 10% and 25% cement replacement with FA exhibited higher 28-day CS compared to standard concrete. However, replacing 35% of cement with FA resulted in a decrease in the ultimate CS of the concrete.

IV. IMPACT OF SIGNIFICANT FA CONTENT ON FRESH CONCRETE PROPERTIES

A. *Setting Time:*

According to the Indian Standard (IS) code, especially IS 4031 (Part 5):1988, the setting time is the amount of time it takes for the cement paste to reach the desired consistency. Portland cement is a critical element in concrete production because it commences the setting process. Nevertheless, incorporating FA into the concrete mixture significantly affects the setting time of the cement, causing a noticeable delay compared to concrete formulations devoid of FA, in accordance with the guidelines outlined in the relevant IS code. According to IS 4031 (Part 5):1988, using FA consistently extends the setting time of the cement in concrete compositions. This extension occurs with variable amounts of FA substitution. Experimental studies consistently show that when FA is present in the mixture, incorporating FA results in noticeable delays in both the initial and final setting times of the concrete. Particularly, the first setting time, indicating the duration for the cement paste to attain a specified level of stiffness, is significantly prolonged with the addition of FA. This delay is determined by the type of FA utilised and the proportion put into the concrete mix. Experimental findings reveal that the initial setting time can be delayed anywhere between 20 minutes to as long as 4 hours and 20 minutes when FA is incorporated. Similarly, when FA is added to the mixture, the final setting time, which indicates when the cement paste reaches its ultimate rigidity, is pushed back. The type and quantity of FA used impact the duration of the delay. The addition of FA can extend the final setting time by varying durations, ranging from one hour to five hours and fifteen minutes, as indicated by experimental findings. The delay in setting time is influenced by crucial factors such as the chemical composition, particle size distribution, and pozzolanic activity of the FA. According to the provisions of the relevant IS code, the setting time characteristics of concrete incorporating FA must be carefully monitored and accounted for during construction projects, taking into account the potential deviations from standard setting times observed in conventional concrete compositions. Engineers and construction professionals can efficiently evaluate and control the setting properties of concrete containing FA by following the standards outlined in the IS code, which include appropriate testing procedures and setting time monitoring. This knowledge enables informed decision-making during the concrete placement and curing processes, ensuring the desired workability and setting properties while also capitalizing on the benefits of FA incorporation in terms of increased sustainability and resource conservation.

B. *Workability ,Water Requirement:*

According to the Indian Standard (IS) code, especially IS 3812 (Part 1):2013, the incorporation of FA in concrete mixtures often results in a reduction in the amount of water required to achieve constant workability. However, it is crucial to remember that the degree of water reduction varies depending on the FA employed. In accordance with IS 3812 (Part1):2013, the presence of FA in fresh concrete has various advantages. One notable advantage is better workability of the concrete mix. Workability is the ease with which concrete may be mixed, put, compacted, and finished during construction operations. When FA is added to the mixture, it improves its ability to work by reducing the need for mixing water. This reduced water demand provides for greater control over the consistency and flow behavior of the concrete, making it easier to handle and put on the construction site. The use of FA in concrete optimizes workability and provides various practical benefits. It improves the capacity to mould and shape the concrete, allowing for more efficient construction procedures. Furthermore, greater workability allows for better consolidation and compaction of the concrete, resulting in a denser, more uniform structure. This increases the overall durability

and strength of the hardened concrete. Furthermore, integrating FA reduces water requirements, which has economic and environmental benefits. By reducing the amount of mixing water, the overall cementitious material composition in the concrete can be successfully optimized, lowering material costs. Furthermore, a lower water-cement ratio improves hydration and reduces drying shrinkage in concrete, improving long-term performance and reducing the possibility of cracks and deformations. In addition, the incorporation using FA in concrete encourages environmentally friendly building methods. FA is a byproduct of coal combustion, and using it as a supplementary cementitious material helps to reduce waste and the environmental impact. By mixing FA, a waste item, into concrete, it can be efficiently used to save natural resources and reduce the carbon footprint associated with cement manufacturing.

V. IMPACT OF SIGNIFICANT FA CONTENT ON HARDENED CONCRETE PROPERTIES

The impact of significant FA content on hardened concrete properties is an important aspect to consider, particularly because FA is commonly used as an additional cementitious material utilized in the production of concrete.

A. Strength:

The addition of FA significantly modifies the strength of concrete, a critical characteristic. However, the extent of this impact heavily depends on the water-to-cement (w/c) ratio utilized in the concrete mixture. When FA is employed as a partial substitute for Portland cement, the initial strength of the concrete is frequently diminished in comparison to compositions solely comprising pure Portland cement. Various factors contribute to FA's influence on concrete strength. An essential attribute is the pozzolanic property of FA, wherein it reacts with calcium hydroxide in the presence of water to produce supplementary cementitious compounds. This mechanism aids in augmenting the overall strength of the concrete. However, in early stages of hydration, when rapid strength increase is sought, the pozzolanic activity of FA may not proceed as quickly as that of pure Portland cement. As a result, the early strength of the concrete may be slightly diminished when FA is added. The level of strength reduction in FA-containing concrete is affected by the w/c ratio. A larger w/c ratio usually results in more dramatic declines in early strength. This is because increased water content dilutes cementitious elements, particularly FA, affecting total strength development. In contrast, with a lower w/c ratio, the influence of FA. While the use of FA in concrete can result in lower early strength, it is critical to evaluate the long-term strength gains. As the concrete cures and ages, the pozzolanic reaction of FA progresses, leading to the gradual development of strength. Consequently, the strength of concrete containing FA may eventually equal or even surpass that of concrete made with pure Portland cement. It is worth mentioning that the strength reduction in early phases is frequently overcome by other advantages afforded by FA, such as improved workability, reduced heat of hydration, increased durability, and reduced permeability. The overall efficacy and appropriateness of FA-containing concrete for a specific application should be evaluated in light of the intended strength requirements and project specifications.

B. Curing:

According to the Indian Standard (IS) code, especially IS 1489 (Part 1):1991, the addition of FA to cement paste requires a longer period of moist curing than pure cement paste. The IS code defines standards and specifications for incorporating FA into concrete, with a focus on changing curing requirements due to FA's pozzolanic nature. The regulation underscores the importance of prolonged moist curing to facilitate optimal hydration and strength development in pastes containing FA. The IS code recognizes that pastes containing FA are more sensitive to relative humidity than pastes without FA. To achieve the best outcomes, moisture conditions must be carefully monitored and controlled during the curing process due to their increased sensitivity. The IS code's suggested moist curing time for FA-containing pastes varies based on the type and proportion of FA used, the ambient temperature, and the desired strength requirements. Adhering to the IS code criteria helps ensure that the FA particles react well with the cementitious matrix, increasing the overall strength and longevity of the concrete. By following the provisions of the IS code, construction professionals can ensure that the curing process for FA-containing pastes is appropriately managed.

VI. PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS:

The collection system type and the temperature of combustion of pulverized coal primarily influence the physical characteristics of FA, such as fineness, particle shape, size, density, and color.

TABLE -II:
PHYSICAL REQUIREMENTS OF FLY ASH AS PER (BIS)

SN.	Characteristics	Requirements (Siliceous and Calcareous Fly Ash)
1	Fineness- Specific surface in m ² /kg. (Min.)	320
2	Particle retained- on 45-micron IS sieve in % (Max.)	34
3	Lime reactivity- in N/mm ² , (Min.)	4.5
4	CS-at 28days in N/mm ² , (Min.)	Not less than 80% of the strength of plain cement mortar cubes
5	Soundness by auto clave test-Expansion in % (Max.)	0.8

TABLE -III:
PHYSICAL REQUIREMENTS OF FLY ASH AS PER (ASTM)

SN.	Characteristics	Requirements (Siliceous and Calcareous Fly ash)
1	Particle retained- on 45-micron IS sieve in % (Max.)	34
2	Water requirement- in % on control, (Max.)	105
3	Strength Activity index –with Portland cement at 7 and 28 days, in %, (Min.)	75
4	Soundness by auto clave test-Expansion in % (Max.)	0.8

VII.CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS:

FA, a finely divided material, is predominantly composed of chemical constituents such as SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, and CaO, which account for its pozzolanic properties. The general range of the principal elements is as follows: SiO₂ (25-60%), Al₂O₃ (10-30%), and Fe₂O₃ (5-25%).

TABLE -IV:
CHEMICAL REQUIREMENTS OF FLY ASH (AS PER BIS)

SN.	Characteristics	Requirements	
		Siliceous Fly Ash	Calcareous Fly Ash
1	SiO ₂ +Al ₂ O ₃ +Fe ₂ O ₃ (% by mass, Min.)	70	50
2	SiO ₂ (% by mass, Min.)	35	25
3	Reactive silica (% by mass, Min.)	20	20
4	MgO (% by mass, Max.)	5	5
5	SO ₃ (% by mass, Max.)	3	3
6	Na ₂ O (% by mass, Max.)	1.5	1.5
7	Total Chlorides (% by mass, Max.)	0.05	0.05
8	Loss on Ignition (% by mass, Max.)	5	5

TABLE -V:
CHEMICAL REQUIREMENTS OF FLY ASH (AS PER ASTM)

SN.	Characteristics	Requirements	
		Siliceous Fly Ash	Calcareous Fly Ash
1	SiO ₂ +Al ₂ O ₃ +Fe ₂ O ₃ (% by mass, Min.)	70	50
2	Moisture Content (% by mass, Max.)	3	3
3	SO ₃ (% by mass, Max.)	5	5
4	Loss on Ignition (% by mass, Max.)	6	6

VIII.MATERIALS USED:

A variety of materials are utilized, including FA, cement, sand, fine aggregate, and coarse aggregate. Laboratory investigations focused on the physical parameters of cement, FIA, CA, FA, and water utilized in the mix design of M20 grade concrete, as outlined below.

A.Cement:

OPC 53 cement was employed in this study, adhering to the specifications outlined in IS456: 2000. The physical characteristics of the cement utilized are presented in Table VI below.

TABLE-VI: PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF CEMENT

Properties	Test Values
Specific Gravity	3.10 g/cc
Consistency (%)	31
Initial Setting Time	91 min.
Final Setting Time	211 min.

B. Fine Aggregates:

Locally sourced sand that passed through a 4.75mm IS sieve was utilized to produce the FIA. The physical characteristics of the FIA are detailed in Table VII below.

TABLE-VII:
PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF FINE AGGREGATES

Properties	Test Values
Specific Gravity	2.60
Water Absorption	1%

C. Coarse Aggregates:

CA, conforming to Indian standards, were utilized with nominal optimal aggregate sizes of 20mm (60%) and 10mm (40%). The physical attributes of the CA are delineated in the following Table VIII

TABLE-VIII:
PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF COARSE AGGREGATES

Properties	CA-20	CA-10
Type	Crushed	Crushed
Specific Gravity	2.65	2.70
Water Absorption	0.50%	0.50%

D.Fly Ash:

The FA employed belonged to class F and possessed a specific gravity of 2.10.FA is collected from Bandel Thermal Power Station, a coal-fired power plant located on the western bank of the Hooghly River in West Bengal.

E.Water:

The water utilised for the experiments was drinkable.

IX.TEST ON INGREDIENT OF FA CONCRETE:

Testing ingredients of FA concrete involves evaluating the properties and performance of its components.

A.Particle Size Distribution Of FA:

To ascertain particle size distribution, sieve analysis is employed. Begin by placing one kilogram of dry FA onto the uppermost sieve of the sieve shaker, equipped with a range of brass sieves. Position the pan at the bottom and affix the cover atop the sieve shaker. Initiate shaking for 10 to 15 minutes. Upon cessation of shaking, deactivate the sieve shaker and measure the material retained on each sieve.

TABLE -IX:
WEIGHT RETAINED ON EACH SIEVE

SN.	Sieve Size (mm)	Weight Retained (gram)	% weight retained	Cumulative % weight retained	% Finer
1	4.75	45	4.5	4.5	95.5
2	2.36	65	6.5	11.0	89.0

B. Fineness Test Of FA:

The significance of FA fineness lies in its impact on both the rate of pozzolanic activity and the workability of concrete. Specifications mandate a minimum of 66 percent passage through the 0.044 mm (No. 325) sieve. For measuring fineness, the wet sieving method utilizing a 45-micron sieve is recommended, aligning with various international standards.

TABLE -X:
DETERMINE THE FINENESS OF FLY ASH BY 45 MICRON SIEVE:

SN.	Sieve Size (micron)	Weight of sample taken (In gram)	Weight of retained Sample Taken (In gram)	% Fineness
1	45	100	21	21

X.METHODOLOGY:

The principal objective of this study is to comprehensively examine the impacts of FA on two fundamental properties of concrete: CS and workability. This is accomplished by partially substituting cement with variable amounts of FA, ranging from 0% to 50%. To achieve consistency, the concrete mix followed the IS456:2000 requirements, using an M20 grade mix design ratio of 1:1.5:3 (Cement: Sand: Aggregate) and keeping the water-to-cement (w/c) ratio between 0.45 and 0.60. To support the experimental inquiry, 72 cubes measuring 150mm x 150mm are precisely cast. Six slump cones are also meticulously prepared, with measurements of 300mm in height, 200mm in diameter at the base, and 100mm in diameter at the top. Out of the 72 cubes, a batch of 12 was used to test the CS of standard concrete without any FA. Sets of 12 cubes were cast to ascertain the CS values

for each specified replacement level (10%, 25%, 35%, 40%, and 50%). Similarly, one slump cone is used to assess the workability of standard concrete without FA additive. Slump cones are distributed to each replacement level in a parallel manner, allowing the workability of various combinations to be assessed. Workability is defined as the difference in height between the mould and the average sinking value. Four cubes from each set of 12 cubes for the replacement levels are chosen to test CS after three days of curing, while the remaining eight cubes are set aside for CS testing at seven and 28 days, respectively. A contemporary Compression Testing Machine with a powerful 2000kN capability is utilised to precisely assess the compressive load applied to concrete specimens of varying ages. The CS of concrete is determined by computing the ratio between the final load applied and the cross-sectional area of the cubes, each of which measured 150mm x 150mm. The workability assessment, on the other hand, focused on evaluating the height difference between the mould and the average subsidence value, which provided useful information about the flow characteristics of the concrete mixtures.

The study's goal is to gain a complete understanding of how FA incorporation influences concrete's workability and CS through this extensive experimental endeavour. The study contributes to the body of knowledge by highlighting the acceptability and potential applications of concrete mixtures containing various percentages of FA.

Figure I: Concrete Mixed for CS Test

XI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

□ Each set of four cubes of M20 grade concrete was tested in a Compression Testing Machine with 0%, 10%, 25%, 35%, 40%, and 50% cement replacement with FA to assess CS after three, seven, and twenty-eight days. Average value of these 4 readings gives the average CS of concrete.

□ At 3 days, 7 days, and 28 days, the average CS of cubes was 8.16 N/mm², 13.05 N/mm², and 19.6 N/mm² for standard concrete without FA. However, when 50% of cement was replaced with FA, it decreased to 4.9 N/mm², 8.09 N/mm², and 13.05 N/mm², respectively. The CS of M20 grade concrete for various quantities of FA after 3, 7, and 28 days of curing are shown in tables XI, XII, and XIII, respectively.

□ It has also been noted that as the amount of FA increases, so does the slump value, indicating an increase in workability. The Slump values are also reported in Table XIV.

TABLE -XI:
CS OF M20 GRADE OF CONCRETE FOR DIFFERENT PROPORTIONS OF FA AT THE AGE OF 3 DAYS:

Mix	3 days curing		
	Load(k N)	CS(N/mm ²)	ACS(N/mm ²)
0% FA	180	8	8.16
	177	7.86	
	190	8.4	
	189	8.4	
10% FA	243	10.8	9.87
	225	10	
	218.25	9.7	
	202.5	9	
25% FA	195	8.67	8.72
	200.7	8.92	
	195.7	8.71	
	193.72	8.61	

35% FA	146.25	6.5	6.28
	152.78	6.79	
	130.5	5.8	
	136	6.04	
40% FA	128.25	5.7	5.32
	123.75	5.5	
	114.75	5.1	
	112.5	5	
50% FA	117	5.2	4.9
	110.25	4.9	
	110.25	4.9	
	103.75	4.61	

TABLE -XII:
CS OF M20 GRADE OF CONCRETE FOR DIFFERENT PROPORTIONS OF FA AT THE AGE OF 7 DAYS:

Mix	7 days curing		
	Load(kN)	CS(N/mm ²)	ACS(N/mm ²)
0% FA	270	12	13.05
	303.75	13.5	
	292.5	13	
	308.25	13.7	
10% FA	396.23	17.61	16.75
	382.5	17	
	371.25	16.5	
	357.75	15.9	
25% FA	292.5	13	13.22
	287.77	12.79	
	295.2	13.12	
	315	14	
35% FA	213.75	9.5	9.99
	210.6	9.36	
	229.5	10.2	
	245.25	10.9	

40% FA	202.5	9	8.73
	198	8.8	
	195.52	8.69	
	190.13	8.45	
50% FA	188.77	8.39	8.09
	183.6	8.16	
	180	8	
	175.95	7.82	

TABLE -XIII:
CS OF M20 GRADE OF CONCRETE FOR DIFFERENT PROPORTIONS OF FA AT THE AGE OF 28 DAYS:

Mix	28 days curing		
	Load(kN)	CS(N/mm ²)	ACS(N/mm ²)
0% FA	427.5	19	19.6
	450	20	
	446	19.8	
	445	19.77	
10% FA	609.7	27.1	26.3
	585	26.66	
	598.5	25.77	
	579.8	26	
25% FA	472.5	21	21.6
	515.2	22.9	
	465.7	20.7	
	490.5	21.8	
35% FA	402.7	17.9	16.92
	382.5	17	
	378	16.8	
	360	16	
40% FA	339.9	15.11	14.78
	319.9	14.22	
	337.5	15	
	333	14.8	

50% FA	312.75	13.9	13.05
	292.5	13	
	270	12	
	299.9	13.33	

TABLE -XIV:

SLUMP VALUE FOR WORKABILITY TEST:

<u>Mix</u>	<u>Slump Value in mm</u>
00% FA	110
10% FA	130
25% FA	140
35% FA	145
40% FA	160
50% FA	165

XII. CONCLUSION:

Through experimental studies including the substituted portion of cement with 10%, 25%, 35%, 40%, and 50% of FA in M20 grade concrete, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Varying percentages of FA in concrete had a significant impact on CS. At 10% and 25%, higher strengths were observed, indicating a positive effect. However, at 35%, 40%, and 50%, CS declined, suggesting a potential negative impact with increased FA levels.
2. FA significantly improved the workability of concrete, making it easier to mix, place, and finish. The finer particles of FA filled gaps between coarser aggregates, improving flow and lubrication. This improved workability led to increased construction efficiency.
3. The addition of FA had a favourable effect on cement consistency, with more FA resulting in better consistency. The finer particle size of FA filled the gaps between cement particles, resulting in a denser and more homogeneous cement paste. This improved the overall performance and cohesion of the concrete mixture.

4. When substituting FA with cement, exercise caution to avoid severe CS losses. Concrete with 10% and 25% FA substitution has higher CS for 28 days than conventional concrete, but when 35% of the cement is replaced with FA, the ultimate CS of the concrete diminishes.

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